

Synthesis of N-Isonicotinyl-3-Methyl-4-(Substituted Hydrazono)-2-Pyrazolin-5-One

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Isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH) and their derivatives are generally used as antitubercular and antitumor agent. We synthesised N¹-isonicotinyl-3-methyl-4-(substituted hydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-one and their derivatives.

THE chemistry¹ and wide range of pharmaceutical properties of 2-pyrazolin-5-one derivatives like germicides², antimicrobial agents³, antiactives⁴, antidiuretics⁵, analgesics and antipyretics⁶, antifungals⁷, antihistaminics⁸, anti M.tuberculosis⁹, antirheumatics¹⁰, antibacterial¹¹ and similar such diseases have been cited in literature. Sulpha drugs are well known chemotherapeutic agents. Isonicotinic acid¹², isonicotinic acid hydrazide¹³ and their derivatives are generally used as antitubercular and antitumor agents.

The method of preparation of 2-pyrazolin-5-one was first reported by Knorr¹⁴. Since then many new methods of synthesising the substituted 2-pyrazolin-5-one and their derivatives have been developed¹⁵.

The present paper reports the reactions of diazotised sulpha drugs and aromatic amines at reactive methylene sites of β -ketoesters forming sulphasubstituted, phenyl hydrazono ethyl-2,3-dioxobutyrate¹⁶. The condensed product on cyclisation with INH gives N-isonicotinyl-3-methyl-4-(substituted hydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-one.

N¹-isonicotinyl-3-methyl-4-(X)-hydrazono-2-pyrazolin-5-one :

where

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 621 Grading IR spectrophotometer. Solution spectra were measured in nujol mulls and KBr disc. The compounds were analysed for nitrogen on Coleman analyser and data were found well in agreement, within limits of the possible experimental error, with calculated values. The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested through TLC.

Synthesis of N-isonicotinyl-3-methyl-4-(X) hydrazono-2-pyrazolin-5-one :

Isonicotinic acid hydrazide (0.005 mole) and substituted phenyl hydrazono-ethyl-2,3-dioxobutyrate (0.005 mole) were dissolved in sufficient quantity of glacial acetic acid and contents were refluxed on a water bath for three hours. On cooling, a solid coloured compound separated out. Filtered, dried and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid/DMF.

By adopting similar procedure, a few substituted-2-pyrazolin-5-ones have been synthesised and their characteristics are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF N-ISONICOTINYL-3-METHYL-4-(X)-HYDRAZONO-2-PYRAZOLIN-5-ONE

Sl. No.	X	m.p.°C	Colour
1.	2.	3.	4.
1.	3-Chlorophenyl	185	DY
2.	4-Chlorophenyl	212	PY
3.	2-Methoxyl phenyl	227	O
4.	3-Methoxyl phenyl	155	RB
5.	4-Methoxyl phenyl	197	SDO
6.	2-Methyl phenyl	220	SDOF
7.	4-Methyl phenyl	192	SON
8.	3-Nitro, 4-methyl phenyl	225	DY
9.	4-Amino diaryl	248	SLBN
10.	2-Chloro, 4-nitrophenyl	233(d)	PY
11.	2,4,6-Tribromophenyl	202	BY
12.	N-Aceto-4-aminophenyl	230	B
13.	1-Naphthyl	257	SLBN
14.	2-Naphthyl	245	SDBN
15.	2-Sulphanilamido benzene	248	SOF
16.	N ¹ -2-Pyridyl sulphanilamido-benzene	245	DY
17.	N ¹ -2-Thiazolyl sulphanilamido-benzene	243	LO
18.	N ¹ -2-Pyrimidyl sulphanilamido-benzene	249	DY
19.	N ¹ -2-Guanyl sulphanilamido-benzene	250	DeY

(Table 1 Contd.)

20.	N ¹ -2-Acetyl sulphanilamido-benzene	230	PY
21.	N ¹ -2-(4,6-dimethyl)-pyrimidyl sulphanilamido-benzene	255	DY
22.	N ¹ -2-Quinoxalyl sulphanilamido-benzene	172	B
23.	2,3-Dimethyl-1-phenyl- pyrazolone	210	SPeN
24.	4-Carboxyl phenyl	245	PY

(i) Elemental analysis of the compounds were found satisfactory.

(ii) Yield of the compounds ranged between 70 to 85%.

(iii) D=dark, De=dull, P=pale, Y=yellow, Pe=pink, S=shining, N=needles, B=brown, F=flakes, R=red, O=orange, L=light and (d)=decomposed.

IR Spectra :

The spectra had characteristic peaks 780 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ring), 1520 cm⁻¹ (>C=C-NH-N=), 1741 cm⁻¹ (>C=O) amide, 1672 cm⁻¹ (>C=O) cyclic, 1613 cm⁻¹ (>C=N), 1560 cm⁻¹ (heterocyclic five membered 2-pyrazolin-5-one ring) and 1480 cm⁻¹ (six membered heterocyclic pyridine ring) were recorded which helps in establishing the structure of the compounds.

NMR Spectra :

The structure of 2-pyrazolin-5-ones were also confirmed by NMR spectra studies.

2-Pyrazolin-5-one :

NMR (CDCl₃) δ 2.48 (s, 3H, CH₃), 7.07-7.84 [(m, 8H, aromatic (two)] and 8.13-8.24 (s, 1H, -NH).

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